

SCORBUTUS IN INFANTS.

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New York Medical Journal 1894;LIX(May 26):641-646.

<https://resource.nlm.nih.gov/101747078>

<https://archive.org/details/101747078.nlm.nih.gov>

<https://babel.hathitrust.org/cgi/pt?id=nnc2.ark:/13960/t5v724829&seq=655>

An earlier report by Northrup (1892) appears to be the first description of infantile scurvy in the USA: Northrup WP. Scorbustus in infants. Archives of Pediatrics. 1892;IX:1-22.

<https://babel.hathitrust.org/cgi/pt?id=uva.3470143072&seq=13>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15463671>

In a short 1895 paper, Northrup summarized the main features of infant scurvy very briefly.¹

These reports by Northrup were followed by the American Pediatric Society's Collective Investigation (1898) which analyzed 379 cases of infant scurvy seen by 138 observers:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15282390>

The first report of infantile scurvy in Europe appears to be by Danish physician Ingerslev (1871):

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15424739>

Summaries of the history of infantile scurvy:

Still GF. Infantile scurvy: its history. Arch Dis Childhood 1935;10:211-218.

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC1975442>

Evans PR. Infantile scurvy: the centenary of Barlow's disease. Br Med J. 1983;287:1862-3.

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC1550031>

Hess AF. Scurvy, Past and Present. 1920:1-22.

<https://www.gutenberg.org/ebooks/40505>

<https://digital.library.cornell.edu/catalog/chla2903792>

Yellow is used to indicate the most relevant sections.

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This text is available together with the scanned version at:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15463816>

1 Northrup WP. Infantile scorbutus.

AMERICAN GYNÆCOLOGICAL AND OBSTETRICAL JOURNAL, May, 1895.

<https://resource.nlm.nih.gov/101762617>

Read by title before the Medical Society of the State of New York, Albany, February 5, 1895.

“*Diagnosis.*—‘Rheumatism’ of the legs and spongy gums are sufficient basis for naming the disease. Unusual sensitiveness on handling especially if the search seems to show that the child’s legs are the seat of trouble, should cause suspicion. To confirm this diagnosis inquire into the history of feeding. Scurvy may be mistaken for rheumatism, stomatitis, rickets, sarcoma, osteitis, and infantile paralysis.”

“*Diagnosis.*—If the mother says ‘rheumatism’ of the legs, and you find spongy gums—*that’s scurvy!*”

Northrup WP, Crandall FM. **Scorbutus in infants.**²

New York Medical Journal 1894;LIX(May 26):641-646.

<https://resource.nlm.nih.gov/101747078>

<https://archive.org/details/101747078.nlm.nih.gov>

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15463816>

The first-mentioned writer, when he saw at the Foundling Asylum in 1889 a child suffering from scurvy,³ groped among several diseases for an explanation of the symptoms. No diagnosis having been made, the baby was not treated for scurvy, and, not being treated for scurvy, it died. The post mortem findings revealed the true nature of the disease. This was the first case of undoubted scorbutus in an infant recorded in the medical literature of the United States, and it is yet the only case completed by a full autopsy record. A few cases of cachexia thought to be scorbutic had been seen by Jacobi and Forchheimer, but had never found their way into indexed literature.

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Two years later the writer met with a typical case in consultation. This was in rich surroundings, was instantly recognized, treated, and quickly cured. These two cases compass the entire field. One, a foundling undiagnosed, came to autopsy, showing typical lesions. The second, early diagnosed and promptly treated, was better in a few days, and well in a month. The first might be an institution curiosity, but the second brought the disease into the field of the general practitioner.

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Being suspicious that scurvy might be of occasional occurrence in general practice, the same writer, in 1891 set about finding cases like the two in his possession. The surgeon general's office could furnish but one possible but not typical case. In New York and vicinity seven well marked cases, by dint of search, were added to the two, also two more less definite—making a total of eleven. These eleven cases were reported in a paper read before the American Pædiatric Society in September, 1891.⁴

2 Based on a paper read by Dr. Northrup before the New York Academy of Medicine, February 15, 1894, and on clinical material collected and edited by Dr. Crandall.

3 This is Case 2 in the Table at the end of this report. The Table shows 36 cases of scurvy characterized by surroundings, symptoms, lesions, signs, treatment, course. See the scanned Table at:

<https://resource.nlm.nih.gov/101747078>

The same case is also Case II in footnote 4.

4 Northrup WP. Scorbutus in infants. Archives of Pediatrics. 1892;IX:1-22.

<https://babel.hathitrust.org/cgi/pt?id=uva.3470143072&seq=13>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15463671>

The important features in the pathological anatomy of scurvy are well illustrated in the asylum case already referred to. The gums showed the characteristic signs of hæmorrhagic gingivitis, being dark, spongy, and bloody. The main interest otherwise lay in the condition of the legs. The left thigh was symmetrically enlarged, but both thighs were above normal in size. The femur was normal at its upper extremity. The lower half was invested with a black, grumous, subperiosteal layer of blood. The lower epiphysis was detached and the lower end of the shaft macerated, eroded, and soft, lying loose in the black, disintegrating blood clot. The tibiæ were surrounded by thin, dark, hæmorrhagic layers beneath the periosteum, and the proximal portions of both were congested. The fibulæ and the bones of the upper extremities were normal. The accompanying illustration was drawn from a specimen which consisted of a lateral half of the lower limb of the less affected side. Microscopical examination of the bone disclosed no syphilitic or rhachitic changes, and no inflammatory changes in bone or periosteum. The softened, macerated bone gave no evidence of suppuration, but there was moderate congestion of the femur and the upper extremity of the tibia.

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Figure. A vertical section of the thigh and leg in a case of infantile scorbutus (Case 2 in the table ⁵). The dark areas along the femur and tibia represent subperiosteal hæmorrhage. (Drawn from a specimen preserved in the museum of the College of Physicians and Surgeons.)⁵

All the lesions of scurvy are hæmorrhagic in character, due probably to diapedesis⁶. The most characteristic are subperiosteal hæmorrhages, chiefly of the long bones. The femora are most commonly affected and there is a tendency to separation of the epiphyses. Hæmorrhages into the mucous surfaces are usually present, the gums being chiefly affected, presenting a condition to which the term hæmorrhagic gingivitis may be appropriately applied. Deep hæmorrhages into the muscles are also of frequent occurrence.

5 See the scanned Table and Figure in:
<https://resource.nlm.nih.gov/101747078>
<https://archive.org/details/101747078.nlm.nih.gov>
<https://babel.hathitrust.org/cgi/pt?id=nnc2.ark:/13960/t5v724829&seq=655>

6 Diapedesis.
https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Leukocyte_extravasation

Eustace Smith⁷ believes subperiosteal hæmorrhage to be the most characteristic lesion of the disease. Strümpell⁸ says that deep extravasations are the peculiarity of scurvy, and that next in importance is the peculiar condition of the gums and mucous membrane of the mouth.

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That infantile scurvy is not simply a rare curiosity among diseases is proved by the fact that **at a meeting of the Academy of Medicine on February 15th a hundred and six cases were reported. Eight cases have since been added to the list, making a total of a hundred and fourteen authentic cases.** Dr. Louis Starr, of Philadelphia, in a communication read at this meeting, reported thirteen cases, all in private practice and in the best of surroundings. All the patients recovered except one. The autopsy findings in that case were identical with those reported in this article. Dr. Forchheimer, of Cincinnati, in a communication read at the same meeting, reported ten cases. He believed that the diagnosis rested upon the hæmorrhagic nature of the symptoms, and that all conditions classed under the head of purpura, peliosis, etc., were in fact scorbutic in nature. He referred to the **peculiar muddy complexion** which was common in these cases, and **laid especial stress upon the result of treatment as an important point in the diagnosis.** Dr. Rotch, of Boston, had seen nearly forty cases. He was in serious doubt whether such a disease as acute rhachitis existed. Some of his cases had been superadded to rhachitis. After recovery of the scurvy, the rhachitis took the usual slow course. Dr. Blackader, of Montreal, and Dr. Booker, of Baltimore, had not met with scurvy in infants.

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- 7 Smith, Eustace. On the Wasting Diseases of Infants and Children.
<https://archive.org/details/onwastingdiseas03smitgoog/page/n134/mode/2up> (NY 1884, p.108)
<https://archive.org/details/onwastingdiseas00smitgoog/page/n166/mode/2up> (London 1884, p.141)
<https://archive.org/details/onwastingdiseas01smitgoog/page/n165/mode/2up> (1899, p.143)
A Practical Treatise on Diseases in Children.
<https://archive.org/details/apracticaltreat00smitgoog/page/252/mode/2up> (1884, p.253)
<https://archive.org/details/apracticaltreat02smitgoog/page/252/mode/2up> (1884, p.253)
<https://archive.org/details/39002079333051.med.yale.edu/page/252/mode/2up> (1884, p.253)
<https://archive.org/details/39002079333135.med.yale.edu/page/266/mode/2up> (1889, p.266)
<https://archive.org/details/apracticaltreat01smitgoog/page/267/mode/2up> (1889, p.266)
<https://archive.org/details/practicaltreatis00smituoft/practicaltreatis00smituoft/page/266/mode/2up> (1889, p.266)
- 8 Strümpell, Adolf. A text-book of Medicine for Students and Practitioners.
<https://archive.org/details/b2150877x/page/900/mode/2up> (1887, p.901)
<https://archive.org/details/b21981565/page/900/mode/2up> (1887, p.901)
<https://archive.org/details/b28135970/page/956/mode/2up> (1893, p.956)
<https://archive.org/details/b21981553/page/956/mode/2up> (1893, p.956)
<https://archive.org/details/textbookofmedici1893str/page/956/mode/2up> (1893, p.956)
<https://archive.org/details/textbookofmedici1895str/page/956/mode/2up> (1895, p.956)

There is without doubt some uncertainty regarding both the true nature of scurvy and its true causes. There are probably certain obscure hæmorrhagic conditions which are scorbutic in character. The ordinary cases, however, present a remarkably uniform collection of symptoms. A case which occurred in the practice of one of the writers presented the following very typical history of scurvy in an early stage:

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A male child of thirteen months⁹ had been nursed for three months. It was then weaned and fed on cow's milk for four months, then on Nestlé's food, then on Mellin's food with a small proportion of milk, and finally for six weeks, at the advice of a friend, almost exclusively on prepared barley. For several weeks the baby had been fretful and cross and for two weeks had been especially irritable and had evinced pain when handled. It was inclined to lie quiet and was irritable when disturbed. Blood had been noticed twice on the lips, but had been attributed to injury from a rough nipple. Swelling above the right knee had been noticed for twenty-four hours and it was remembered that the child had not moved the leg naturally for several days.

On examination, the child was found to be anæmic and showed moderate signs of rickets. There were four teeth. The gums around each tooth were dark red and spongy, and, on pressure, bled slightly. The slightest movement caused the child to cry out with pain, and this was most marked when the hips or legs were moved or pressed upon. The right thigh was considerably swollen, the skin being tense and slightly red. It was excessively sensitive to pressure, but did not pit. There was also slight tenderness at the hip. The child was drawn up in a peculiar attitude with the legs flexed. On the leg there were one or two spots slightly discolored, but there was no distinct purpura. The treatment consisted solely of top milk, beef juice, and orange juice. Improvement in the gums was noticed in two days. The soreness rapidly decreased, and there was complete recovery from all other symptoms in less than three weeks.

Of the hundred and fourteen cases referred to, a detailed history has been obtained in thirty-six. These histories are presented in the accompanying table³. It has been impossible to enter all the details in many of the histories. Certain facts are referred to, therefore, which do not appear in the table.

9 This is Case 13 in the Table at the end of the scanned report.

Sex is referred to in thirty-two cases—sixteen being males, sixteen females. The youngest patient was four months old, the oldest was an idiot of six years. Twenty-eight children (seventy-nine per cent.) were between eight months and eighteen months; twenty two children (sixty-three per cent.) were between nine months and thirteen months. The disease is most common, therefore, at about the end of the first year of life.

Investigation of the surroundings and social condition shows that twenty-six patients were seen in private practice and ten in institutions or dispensaries. In fourteen the surroundings were stated as being excellent, rich, or luxurious. In but two cases were the surroundings of private patients stated as especially bad. The surroundings of institution patients were especially poor in five instances. Ten of these children lived in the country or in small towns. It is evident that scurvy is not essentially a disease of large cities, and especially not of tenement house regions. Unhygienic surroundings in themselves are clearly not an important feature in its production. Some of the worst cases reported occurred in families in which the children received the most painstaking care. Other causes must therefore be sought.

The most evident and probably the most active cause of scurvy is improper diet. The exact diet is known in thirty-three cases. We find that twelve of these children (thirty-six per cent.) were fed on a proprietary food exclusively; six (eighteen per cent.) had received an exclusive diet of condensed milk or evaporated cream, while three received a combination of these two foods. Over sixty-three per cent., therefore, were fed upon a diet of proprietary foods and condensed milk. Two children received sterilized milk exclusively and three a weak mixture of milk and water. One was fed on condensed milk, one on boiled and peptonized milk, one on barley water. Two were asylum babies who were “boarded out.” In only one was fresh milk the exclusive diet, but it was not stated whether it was given pure or diluted. It is seen, therefore, that improper methods of feeding were pursued in every case with perhaps a single exception. *The experience of most observers agrees with the facts here presented, that the exclusive use of a proprietary food or of evaporated milk is the most common accompaniment of scurvy.* No one food seems to be a special offender, except as it is more generally used. The one food which is probably the most

largely used in this country was mentioned most frequently. Should it come into general use it would no doubt obtain the monopoly on scurvy, though it would probably not exhibit its scurvy cases in its public advertisements.

Sterilized milk also is believed by some to be capable of producing scurvy. The evidence seems to be undoubted that milk sterilized for a long time at a high temperature has caused this disease. The statement made by Holt¹⁰, that in three great institutions of New York city where infants are fed almost exclusively on sterilized milk not a single case of scurvy has developed in five years, would seem to show that where this process is not carried to an unreasonable degree no danger is to be apprehended. No such charge has been made against Pasteurized milk, which is a safer food for a variety of reasons. Sterilized milk requires as careful modification as raw milk. If it is not properly modified it may cause serious disturbance. It is possible, as suggested by Winters, that lack of proper preparation has been a factor in certain cases as well as the sterilization. Sterilized milk has proved too valuable a food in large cities to be thoughtlessly set aside until it is positively proved to be unsafe. Weak milk mixtures seem to have been a causative factor in three cases. One of these, a child of eleven months, was fed upon nothing but milk diluted with an equal amount of water. Winters has recently drawn special attention to the fact that an excessively weak mixture may be an active cause of the disease.

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Anæmia was definitely noted as present in fifteen cases, and as not present in but one case. Metallic pallor or extreme sallowness was observed four times. The nutrition was noted as good in four cases. Malnutrition was specially noted seven times, and marasmus seven times.

Rhachitis was referred to nineteen times. It was to a marked degree present in five cases, and slight rhachitis in six. It was definitely not present in eight cases. In several instances the scurvy was referred to as being ingrafted upon or added to the rickets. When the symptoms of scurvy disappeared under treatment, the rhachitic condition remained unchanged and disappeared slowly. Those who have seen most scurvy seem to be most skeptical as to the existence of such a disease as acute rhachitis. In some cases it is certain that the condition described under that

10 L. Emmett Holt wrote a book chapter about infant scurvy: Holt LE. Scorbutus (Scurvy). In: The Diseases of Infancy and Childhood. 6th ed., 1911:233–241. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15343352>

name is, in fact, scurvy superadded to rickets.

The condition of the bowels was referred to in nine cases. Diarrhœa was present in six; constipation in two. In one case they were regular. Diarrhœa has been especially noticed by Carr.

Fever was frequently noted, and was commonly intermittent in character. It rarely went above 101°, but occasionally reached 103°. It seemed in many instances to be an integral part of the disease, but sometimes it seemed clearly due to other causes.

Pseudo paralysis is an interesting and very important symptom, which may readily mislead the unwary. In a paper read before the Academy of Medicine, Dr. Henry Ling Taylor reported two marked cases. He believed that essential paralysis could not be attributed to scurvy, but that the condition was due to the pain caused by contraction of the muscles on their tender periosteal attachments. This might become so intense that all motion would be instinctively avoided. When joint irritation existed, there would be local reflex muscular rigidity, which would also operate to prevent motion. It was to be distinguished from other paralytic affections by the accompanying symptoms of scurvy, normal knee reflexes, and speedy subsidence on antiscorbutic diet. The spine and upper extremities were sometimes affected, but more commonly the lower extremities were alone involved. Pseudo paralysis was definitely present in nine cases. It involved one leg in one case, both legs in three, legs and arms in one. Two children were reported as perfectly helpless, and in two cases the location was not stated. In no instance did the paralysis persist after the subsidence of the scorbutic symptoms. The diagnosis of infantile paralysis had been made in no fewer than three of these cases, and one had been treated for some time by electricity.

Pain was more common than any other symptom. It was, in fact, present in every patient in whom its presence or absence was noted. It was specified as in the legs in ten cases and in the arms in three. It was usually severe and often so excessive as to cause the child to scream out with fear at the approach of the attendants. It was commonly marked only upon motion or handling. The child suffering from scurvy is therefore inclined to lie quietly in any position in which it is most comfortable. As a rule, the legs are slightly flexed.

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Passages of blood were noted from the stomach in two cases, from the bowels in four, from the nose in two, and from the bladder in two; it was definitely noted as not present in but three patients. In the remaining cases no mention was made of this symptom.

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Subcutaneous hæmorrhages were noted in at least fifteen cases; “purpura” was observed seven times; “petechiæ,” three times; “ecchymoses,” five times. In one child a vaccination scar two months old became ecchymotic. In three cases hæmorrhage took place in the eyelids, causing “black eye,” and adding greatly to the wretched appearance of the little sufferer.

The condition of the gums was noted in thirty two cases. In two instances there were no teeth, and the gums were neither spongy nor bleeding. This peculiarity has been recorded by numerous observers. When a few teeth only have appeared, the changes in the gums are, as a rule, limited to the gums bordering these teeth. In twenty-four cases the gums were described as spongy, inflamed, or purple. In three cases they were described as ulcerated, and in three as simply bleeding. Actual bleeding of the gums was noted in nineteen cases. The condition of the gums was therefore one of the most constant and characteristic symptoms.

Swelling of the extremities was noted in thirty-three cases. The skin over the swelling was, as a rule, tense and shining; it was often purplish or livid, but sometimes appeared normal in color; it was of normal temperature, and did not pit on pressure. As the swelling subsided, thickening of the shaft of the bone was in some instances detected. Liability to fracture at the epiphyses was a marked feature.

In ten cases both legs were said to be involved, and in one leg, but the exact location of the swelling was not mentioned. In the remaining twenty two cases in which the exact location was noted the thigh was involved sixteen times, the leg below the knee thirteen times, the ankle five times, the knee four times, and the arm three times.

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The accompanying table shows the various locations of the lesions:

One thigh	4
Both thighs	4
Both thighs and legs	3
Both thighs, legs, and forearms	2
One thigh and one knee	1
One thigh and one ankle	1
One thigh and one leg	1
Both legs, feet, and scrotum	1
One leg and one humerus	1
Both knees and ankles	3
One ankle	1
	—
Total	22

The results of antiscorbutic treatment are, almost without exception, very brilliant. Many of these children were treated at first by general tonics, acids, phosphorus, or chlorate of potassium. The result of such treatment, without exception, was unsatisfactory. It seemed in most instances to produce no effect whatever upon the course of the disease. The subsequent improvement under antiscorbutic regimen was therefore especially gratifying to the attending physician. The one thing absolutely necessary to insure a cure is fresh food. Fresh cow's milk is, by all means, the most important element. It is both food and medicine. It should be properly diluted and prepared to meet the requirements of the case. It is well to combine it with a cereal, as Jacobi has suggested. If it requires diluting, barley water may be employed. In warm weather it may be Pasteurized, or even moderately sterilized. Expressed beef juice is a valuable adjuvant in many cases. There seems but little doubt also that orange juice is an element of decided value. Children will certainly recover without it if put upon a proper diet, but the evidence seems decided that it aids materially in the cure of these cases. It has the merit of being easily administered, for these little sufferers, without exception, take it with marked avidity. When rhachitis is present it is best to administer phosphorus, which may be given in the form of the official elixir. The condition of the stomach and bowels should also receive attention, and tonics are not contraindicated. It should be clearly understood, however, that all drugs are unavailing for the cure of scurvy, and are secondary to milk, beef juice, and orange

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juice. The swollen and painful extremities may be sometimes relieved by inunctions with oil. The child should be handled with the greatest care, not only to avoid unnecessary suffering, but because there is especial liability to fracture of the bones.

It seems probable that scurvy is increasing in frequency. The more general use of patent and evaporated foods to the exclusion of milk will certainly have the result of increasing the number of these cases. It is quite certain, however, that the disease is not a new one, but has been overlooked or mistaken for some other condition. Excluding the diagnosis of acute rhachitis, rheumatism seems to have been the mistaken diagnosis in the greater number of cases. Several cases have been treated simply as purpura, two or three as ulcerative stomatitis, three as infantile paralysis, and one or two as simple rhachitis. One case within the writer's knowledge was considered to be a sarcoma of the knee; two cases had been treated as osteitis of the knee.

In the light of our present knowledge we may draw the following conclusions:

1. Scurvy may appear at any period of infancy or early childhood, but is most common between the ninth and fourteenth months.

2. The lesions are hæmorrhagic in character, due probably to diapedesis. The most characteristic are subperiosteal hæmorrhages. Hæmorrhages into the muscular tissues, into the skin, and mucous membranes are more or less constant.

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3. It occurs in every grade of the social scale, but is more frequent among the rich than among the poor. The neglected child who eats everything at the table may become rhachitic or marasmic, but he obtains enough fresh food to protect him from scurvy. It very rarely occurs in asylums and hospitals, because in recent years feeding in such institutions has been more rational than in many private families.

4. Lack of fresh food is the most important cause. The use of the proprietary foods and condensed milk produces more scurvy than all other causes combined. Even fresh milk in small proportions is not sufficient to insure protection.

5. Anæmia and malnutrition are almost invariably present;

a peculiar sallow complexion is common.

6. Scurvy is frequently superadded to rhachitis, but in a considerable number of cases no evidences of rhachitis are present. So-called acute rickets is in most cases, probably in all, rickets complicated by scurvy.

7. Pain is a constant symptom; it develops early and is usually intense.

8. A varying degree of immobility of the extremities is common, and is frequently so marked as to simulate paralysis. This pseudo-paralysis disappears with the subsidence of the scorbutic symptoms.

9. Subcutaneous hæmorrhages, as well as hæmorrhages from the cavities of the body, are very common, but are not necessary to a diagnosis of scurvy.

10. The condition of the gums is characteristic. They are purplish, soft, spongy, and bleeding, and frequently show decided ulcerations. When the teeth have not been erupted, changes in the gums are usually slight or entirely absent.

11. Painful swelling of the lower extremities is the most constant symptom; the upper extremities are rarely involved. The thigh is affected more frequently than any other region.

12. Children suffering from scurvy commonly present the following symptoms: Anæmia, intense pain on motion, spongy and bleeding gums, swelling of the lower extremities, usually at the thigh. There may also be purpura or ecchymoses, discharge of blood from the various cavities of the body, and pseudo-paralysis.

13. Scurvy, when untreated, is a very fatal disease; when recognized and properly treated, a rapid and complete cure is usually effected. The result of antiscorbutic treatment is, in fact, one of the most certain means of diagnosis.

14. Scurvy may be mistaken for rheumatism, stomatitis, rickets, sarcoma, osteitis, and infantile paralysis.

15. Scurvy is a dietetic disease and must be cured by dietetic treatment. Fresh milk, beef juice, and orange juice are the most effective remedies.

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[At the end of the Northrup-Crandall report there is a table of the collected cases, which is not copied here. It is available at the scanned version:

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Cases 1 to 11 in that table correspond to Cases I to XI in Northrup (1892) report:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15463671>]